

MODEL FOR IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGICAL PREPAREDNESS OF TRAINEES FOR TEACHING NATURAL SCIENCES BASED ON AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH

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Abstract: This article focuses on revealing the components and stages of teaching methodological preparedness for teaching natural sciences based on an integrative approach during the professional development process, as well as the importance of competencies formed in the process of developing scientific and critical thinking.

Keywords: natural sciences, scientific thinking, critical thinking, reflection, professional activity, creativity skills, intercultural skills, global awareness

In integrative educational technology, the integration of the components of educational content is observed: subject knowledge, skills, and the experience of reproductive and creative activities. The essence of integration reflects all components of the educational content, and various options for implementing the integrative process are possible—between elements of knowledge, between knowledge and skills, between reproductive and productive methods of activity, and others.

The modern practice of the functioning and development of pedagogical systems demonstrates the diversity of integrative approaches in education: integrated subjects, binary lessons, integration within an existing subject, and so on. The growing interest in the problem of integrative approaches in pedagogical education reflects the current global trends of the globalization and technologization of knowledge.

At the same time, the essence of the integrative approach is primarily related to the concept of “integration.” The term *integration* comes from the Latin *integratio* – restoration, completion, that is, the interconnectedness of separate parts and functions of a system or organism into a whole, as well as the process leading to such a state.

In addition to *integration*, concepts such as “system,” “component,” “element,” “complex,” “synthesis,” “structure,” “connection,” “interaction,” “system-forming factor,” and others, which are related to the integrative approach, have firmly entered the conceptual apparatus of various methodological approaches in pedagogy for the analysis of complex, systemic-

whole objects. Despite the widespread use of the concept of “integration,” its essence is still interpreted differently.

According to the literature analysis, methodological scientists have given various definitions to the concept of integration. According to T. B. Kharisov, integration is the process of linking continuity and creating integrity. In education, it can be considered the final stage of a course, where elements of different subjects are harmonized.

For example, the principle of information commonality distinguishes the commonality and integrity of the information base of system components as the basis for integration. The principle of integrated integrity emphasizes the integration of system components, where the “output” of one management process becomes the “input” of the next process. The principle of method commonality requires the use of common methods for implementing the integrated system. The principle of multidimensionality considers the integration of all factors forming the system (technological, material, technical, labor, financial) in the management process across several areas of activity. The principle of complexity involves the integration of system-forming components, taking into account the specific structure of management objects at all levels of management. The principle of homeostasis (maintaining stability) views the integrative system as a feedback-based, self-adjusting information system aimed at maintaining the quality of required management impacts at a stable level. Finally, the principle of parity (decentralization) assumes that all levels of management are equal from the perspective of the definition of an integrated system.

Pedagogical integration is one of the types of scientific integration. From a functional perspective, in pedagogy, integration is usually understood as the interconnectedness of separate parts of a system into a unified whole, the process of combining differentiated parts, bringing them closer, and interrelating them. In some cases, the term “integration” is used in the sense of a result – restoring the holistic essence. In special pedagogy, “integration” is understood as the process of involving people with disabilities into society. It is known that the interpretation of the term “integration” largely depends on the context in which it is used.

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